

Table S1

	<i>Bassiana duperreyi</i>	<i>Lampropholis guichenoti</i>	<i>Niveoscincus coventryi</i>	<i>Niveoscincus ocellatus</i>	<i>Pseudemoia entrecasteauxii</i>	<i>Rhizoprionodon taylori</i>
Taxonomic group	Lizard	Lizard	Lizard	Lizard	Lizard	Shark
Reproductive Mode	Oviparous	Oviparous	Viviparous	Viviparous	Viviparous	Viviparous
Nutritional mode	Lecithotrophy	Lecithotrophy	Lecithotrophy	Placentotrophy	Placentotrophy	Placentotrophy
Number of transcripts	212535	102759	155386	189844	86605	121983
% transcripts annotated	51.68	68.78	59.83	54.96	67.53	28.45
Read alignment percentage	94.13	94.23	93.21	93.24	93.08	84.28
Median transcript length	985	1359	1196	1041	1311	595
BUSCO: % complete	94.4	92.2	94.8	94.7	92.4	89.6
BUSCO: % single copy complete	26.3	18.8	39.7	34.3	33	58.1
BUSCO: % duplicated complete	68.1	73.4	55.1	60.4	59.4	31.5
BUSCO: % fragmented	1.6	2	1	1.5	2	4
BUSCO: % missing	4	5.8	4.2	3.8	5.6	6.4